

Original Article

A Microbiological Investigation of Antibacterial Efficacy of Sandalwood Oil and Mupirocin Against *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* and *Enterococcus Faecalis*

Rhea Fernandes¹, K. Divya Denica¹, Jacinta Lymon¹, B. Dhanashree², Srikant Natrajan¹, Raj Kumar Narkedamalli¹, M. Roma^{1*}¹Manipal College of Dental Sciences, Mangalore, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Karnataka, Manipal, 576104, India²Department of Microbiology, Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Karnataka, Manipal, 576104, India

Received: 18 August 2025

Accepted: 13 October 2025

Published online: 28 October 2025

Keywords: antimicrobial activity, enterococcus faecalis, intracanal medicament, mupirocin, nature-based education, pseudomonas aeruginosa, sandalwood oil, well-being

The root canal is an intricate structure that facilitates the growth of microorganisms, as it is enclosed and lacks an oxygen supply. *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* are frequently associated with retreated teeth or persistent infections, resulting in unsuccessful endodontic treatment. There has been increased interest in essential oils because of their lack of toxic effects. This study aims to evaluate the antimicrobial efficacy of C26H44O9 (mupirocin) and sandalwood oil against *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa* by determining their minimum inhibitory concentrations so that they can be used as intracanal medicaments in endodontic infections. Eight clinical isolates each of *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa* and two control strains were included. The MICs of Mupirocin and Sandalwood oil were determined via the broth dilution technique. The inoculum of each bacterium was prepared in Mueller–Hinton broth (MHB) and incubated for 6 hours. Twofold double dilutions of mupirocin and sandalwood oil were prepared in MHB. Ten microliters of bacterial growth mixture were added to each of these dilutions and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The highest dilution of the antibacterial agent that resulted in no turbidity was taken as the MIC. The MBC was recorded by subculturing 2 µl from the tubes that did not show turbidity. The present study revealed that the MIC and MBC of Sandalwood oil were 0.5 µl/µl for seven *P. aeruginosa* strains, whereas one isolate had an MIC and MBC >0.5. The MICs and MBCs of Sandalwood oil for *E. faecalis* are as follows. C26H44O9 and sandalwood oil act against *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa* at high concentrations and may be used synergistically as intracanal medicaments at low concentrations.

© (2025) Society for Biomaterials & Artificial Organs #20017825

Introduction

Microorganisms clearly play an unambiguous role in pulp space infection [1-5]. Endodontic infections arise in enclosed surroundings, setting them apart from other infections of the oral cavity. The root canal is a complex three-dimensional system. Because they are enclosed areas lacking oxygen, which encourages the development of organisms, they can be used as [3]. Many factors are involved in the failure of endodontic treatment, the most common of which is the persistence of microbes. A wide variety of microorganisms have been extracted from root canals

via common culture methods. However, the array of microbes causing infections at the endodontic canal is neglected since only 50% of the microbes in the dental pulp chamber can be cultivated [2]. According to reports, one of the taxa most often obtained from root canals during retreatment, in cases of unsuccessful endodontic intervention, and from canals with chronic infections is the gram-positive pathogen *Enterococcus faecalis* [9-10]. One of the main contributors to the recurrence of infection in the pulp space system is *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a gram-negative facultative bacterium belonging to Gammaproteobacteria [11,12]. Mupirocin, also known as pseudomonic acid A, is a new antimicrobial drug that differs from conventional antibacterial medications in both its molecular structure and manner of action [13-15]. It was first identified in 1971 in the *Pseudomonas* species *P. fluorescens*, and its main mode of action is to prevent the manufacture of protein in microorganisms [16,17]. Plant essential oils have been employed

* Corresponding author

E-mail address: roma.m@manipal.edu (Dr. Roma M, Associate Professor, Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Manipal College of Dental Sciences Mangalore, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Karnataka, Manipal, 576104, India
Orcid id: 0000-0003-3407-8685)

Table 1: MICs and MBCs of sandalwood oil and mupirocin against *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa*

Isolate	Sandalwood Oil		Mupirocin	
	MIC (%v/v)	MBC (%v/v)	MIC (%v/v)	MBC (%v/v)
E.Faecalis				
9240	50	50	50	50
826	50	50	50	25
8863	50	50	50	25
P.aeruginosa				
9303	0.39	0.20	50	50
9312	50	25	50	50
9304	50	25	50	50

for a broad range of objectives for many years. In recent years, increased attention has been given to essential oils because they do not exhibit toxic effects [4,6,8]. At present, endodontic therapy revolves around the utilization of various root canal irrigants that almost but not completely eradicate these microbes [18-24]. This study investigated the efficacy of mupirocin and Indian sandalwood oil (*Santalum album*) on *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa* so that it could be used as an adjunct to other intracanal medicaments. This study was conducted to assess the antimicrobial activity of mupirocin and sandalwood oil as intracanal medicaments in endodontic infections against *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa*.

Materials and Methods

In this pilot study, a microbiological assay was conducted to evaluate the antimicrobial efficacy of mupirocin and sandalwood oil against

E. faecalis and *P. aeruginosa*. The sources of *E. faecalis* ATCC 29212 and *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, which were used as control strains, were collected from the Department of Microbiology. Eight *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa* strains isolated from clinical samples from the Department of Microbiology were used in this study. The study was initiated after the Institutional Ethical Committee yielded IEC number 21018. In this method, twofold dilutions of mupirocin were obtained from 2% w/w Mupirocin disks in sterile distilled water to determine the MIC. The MICs of mupirocin and sandalwood oil were determined according to CLSI guidelines. Standard strains of *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 27853 and *E. faecalis* ATCC 29212 were employed as controls. Ten microliters of 6-hour-old bacterial growth in MHB, whose turbidity was adjusted to 0.5 MacFarland standard, was used as inoculum to seed different MHB strains containing different concentrations of antibacterial agent, which were then incubated. Twofold dilutions of mupirocin and sandalwood oil were prepared in Mueller Hinton broth (MHB), with a concentration range of 4% (v/v) to 0.016% (v/v) and a 50% initial concentration. The inoculum prepared was then added to each of the prepared dilutions and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The highest dilution of mupirocin and sandalwood oil where turbidity was not visible was the MIC. The minimum MBC was determined by subculturing 2 il from the tubes with the highest dilution that showed turbidity and the next highest dilution that did not show turbidity. The highest dilution of the antibacterial agent that did not cause growth in subculture was taken as the MBC (table 1).

A comparison between the two test agents (mupirocin and sandalwood oil) against *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa* was performed, with the key parameter being the antimicrobial activity of the respective agent. Eight samples were needed in each group, with a 1% alpha error, 90% study power, and a clinically meaningful

Table 2a: Efficacy of various concentrations of sandalwood oil and mupirocin against *P. aeruginosa*

	Categories	N	Agent		Chi square	P value
			Sandalwood Oil N (%)	Mupirocin N (%)		
Concentration 0.5%	Resistant	8	1 (12.5)	7 (87.5)	9	0.003
	Sensitive	8	7 (87.5)	1 (12.5)		
Concentration 0.25%	Resistant	14	7 (87.5)	7 (87.5)	0	1
	Sensitive	2	1 (12.5)	1 (12.5)		
Concentration 0.125%	Resistant	15	7 (87.5)	8 (100)	1.067	0.302
	Sensitive	1	1 (12.5)	0 (0)		
Concentration 0.0625%	Resistant	15	7 (87.5)	8 (100)	1.067	0.302
	Sensitive	1	1 (12.5)	0 (0)		
Concentration 0.03125%	Resistant	15	7 (87.5)	8 (100)	1.067	0.302
	Sensitive	1	1 (12.5)	0 (0)		
Concentration 0.015625%	Resistant	15	7 (87.5)	8 (100)	1.067	0.302
	Sensitive	1	1 (12.5)	0 (0)		
Concentration 0.007812%	Resistant	13	5 (62.5)	8 (100)	3.692	0.055
	Sensitive	3	3 (37.5)	0 (0)		
Concentration 0.0039%	Resistant	15	7 (87.5)	8 (100)	1.067	0.302
	Sensitive	1	1 (12.5)	0 (0)		
Concentration 0.00195%	Resistant	15	7 (87.5)	8 (100)	1.067	0.302
	Sensitive	1	1 (12.5)	0 (0)		
Concentration 0.0009765%	Resistant	16	8 (100)	8 (100)	.	.
	Sensitive	0	0 (0)	0 (0)		
Concentration 0.0004882%	Resistant	0	0 (0)	0 (0)	.	.
	Sensitive	16	8 (100)	8 (100)		
Concentration 0.0002441%	Resistant	15	7 (87.5)	8 (100)	1.067	0.302
	Sensitive	1	1 (12.5)	0 (0)		

difference of 16 units.

The sample density was calculated via the following formula,

$$N = \frac{2(Z_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}} + Z_{1-\beta})^2 \sigma^2}{d^2} = 16$$

The sample size was 8 for *E. faecalis* and 8 for *P. aeruginosa*.

Results

The turbidity of Mueller–Hinton broth was evaluated to calculate the MIC and MBC values, which were then subcultured to determine the evidence of bacterial growth. The same analysis was performed under microbiological expertise.

The Microsoft Excel analysis tool package was used to assess the observed results for each strain. The Mann Whitney U test was used to compare the cases and controls.

There was a significant difference in the MIC and MBC values of Sandalwood oil against *P. aeruginosa* strains 9303, 9312, and 9304, which were greater than the MBC values of Mupirocin, suggesting that Sandalwood oil has minimal antibacterial activity against *P. aeruginosa*.

Similarly, there was a significant difference in the MIC and MBC values of Mupirocin against the *E. faecalis* strains 9240, 826, and 8863, which presented MICs greater than the MBC values in comparison to those of Sandalwood oil, indicating that Mupirocin has minimal antibacterial activity against *E. faecalis*. Tables 2 and 3 show the effective concentration gradients of sandalwood oil and mupirocin against *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Discussion

The complex and enclosed nature of the root canal limits the oxygen supply within it, thereby providing a favourable environment for the proliferation of microorganisms [3]. As stated earlier, *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* are frequently associated with retreatment cases or chronic infections, leading to unsuccessful endodontic treatments [25,26]. A literature search revealed that *E. faecalis* is considered to persist as a superbug and can withstand extremely rough environments with a lack of nutrient sources and high alkalinity [27-31]. A systematic review revealed the abundance of *Enterococcus faecalis* (>50%) in necrotic pulps of permanent teeth requiring endodontic therapy [5].

P. aeruginosa, a gram-negative facultative bacterium, can form highly structured biofilms, possessing efflux pumps and quorum sensing, and adapting to challenging environments contributes to its persistence in root canals [22, 32].

Current reports using the broth dilution technique and agar diffusion method indicate that sodium hypochlorite, chlorhexidine, and MTAD do not eradicate *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa* completely because of their potential to cause harm to both vital and nonvital tissues at relatively high concentrations [21]. These constraints associated with commonly used endodontic irrigants [24] highlight the necessity of discovering more effective antibacterial agents against *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa*.

Mupirocin, a polyketide antibiotic originating from *Pseudomonas fluorescens* NCIMB 10586, is characterized by a core structure composed of monic acid, featuring a pyran ring connected to 9-hydroxynonanoic acid through an ester bond. Its antimicrobial

Table 3: Efficacy of various concentrations of sandalwood oil and mupirocin against *E. faecalis*

	Categories	N	Agent		Chi square	P value
			Sandalwood Oil N (%)	Mupirocin N (%)		
Concentration 0.5%	Resistant	12	6 (75)	6 (75)	0	1
	Sensitive	4	2 (25)	2 (25)		
Concentration 0.25%	Resistant	14	7 (87.5)	7 (87.5)	0	1
	Sensitive	2	1 (12.5)	1 (12.5)		
Concentration 0.125%	Resistant	9	7 (87.5)	2 (25)	6.349	0.012
	Sensitive	7	1 (12.5)	6 (75)		
Concentration 0.0625%	Resistant	11	8 (100)	3 (37.5)	7.273	0.007
	Sensitive	5	0 (0)	5 (62.5)		
Concentration 0.03125%	Resistant	10	8 (100)	2 (25)	9.6	0.002
	Sensitive	6	0 (0)	6 (75)		
Concentration 0.015625%	Resistant	12	8 (100)	4 (50)	5.333	0.021
	Sensitive	4	0 (0)	4 (50)		
Concentration 0.007812%	Resistant	12	8 (100)	4 (50)	5.333	0.021
	Sensitive	4	0 (0)	4 (50)		
Concentration 0.0039%	Resistant	11	8 (100)	3 (37.5)	7.273	0.007
	Sensitive	5	0 (0)	5 (62.5)		
Concentration 0.00195%	Resistant	12	8 (100)	4 (50)	5.333	0.021
	Sensitive	4	0 (0)	4 (50)		
Concentration 0.0009765%	Resistant	13	8 (100)	5 (62.5)	3.692	0.055
	Sensitive	3	0 (0)	3 (37.5)		
Concentration 0.0004882%	Resistant	0	0 (0)	0 (0)	.	.
	Sensitive	16	8 (100)	8 (100)		
Concentration 0.0002441%	Resistant	16	8 (100)	8 (100)	.	.
	Sensitive	0	0 (0)	0 (0)		

action stems from the inhibition of bacterial isoleucyl-tRNA synthetase, a vital enzyme in bacterial protein synthesis. Mupirocin is noteworthy for having a wide range of action against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. Its efficacy remains unaffected by the presence of bodily fluids or organic matter, making it a reliable choice for the topical management of various dermatic infections, including impetigo, and for eliminating *Staphylococcus* nasal carriage in patients [1,19,30].

India has long utilized sandalwood oil, an essential oil that comes from trees in the genus *Santalum* [28], for medicinal purposes [25]. Recently, there has been increased utilization of essential oils against common oral microflora. Azizan et al. conducted a comparative analysis of the antibacterial properties of several sandalwood essential oils from diverse sources. This investigation used a combination of α - and β -santalols in agar dilution and diffusion experiments to examine their antibacterial effects on both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. The antibacterial properties of sandalwood oils with medium or high santalol concentrations were very good. This information serves as a foundation for our discussion of the potential antimicrobial properties of sandalwood oil [26].

A study conducted by Takarada tested various essential oils and assessed their minimum inhibitory concentration and minimum bactericidal concentration. Among the oils tested, Manuka oil demonstrated the greatest ability to inhibit bacterial growth. Furthermore, this research highlighted the adhesion-inhibiting effects of tea tree oil and manuka oil on *P. gingivalis*. This information guided our decision to investigate the antimicrobial and adhesion-inhibiting properties of sandalwood oil in our research [27,28].

An advantage of utilizing sandalwood oil is that it is nontoxic in nature; therefore, it can be an alternative to the currently used root canal irrigants [4,6,8]. Chai W. et al. investigated the effects of antibiotics on *E. faecalis*. Among the antibiotics tested, only erythromycin and oxytetracycline were found to eliminate notorious bacteria in a much more similar way to the Vardan P et al. study of irrigants used against predominant root canal microorganisms [29,7]. Similarly, Joshi et al. assessed the potent antibacterial activity of mupirocin against *Enterococcus faecalis* and suggested that 0.0312% mupirocin outperforms 2% chlorhexidine in root canal preparation, emphasizing its potential as a superior final irrigant that is unaffected by tissue fluids and organic debris, suggesting that mupirocin is a promising alternative in endodontic treatments.

In an in-vitro study conducted by Fritz et al., aqueous extracts of thyme, oregano, lemongrass, melaleuca, and clove essential oils were assessed for their effectiveness against *E. faecalis* ATCC 29212. The microdilution method was employed to test the root canals of seven teeth. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values for *E. faecalis* were found to be Thyme (12.5%), Oregano (25%), Lemongrass (50%), Melaleuca (50%), and Clove (50%) [20].

The goal of Man et al.'s study was to evaluate the antibacterial efficacy of several essential oils against *P. aeruginosa* and other gram-positive bacteria. This was achieved through broth microdilution methods and by obtaining homogenous micelle aggregates and aqueous solutions. The most significant antimicrobial activity was observed in micelle suspensions of essential oils, with MICs and MBCs ranging from 0.1% to >50% v/v. Conversely, aqueous extracts exhibited lower levels of bacteriostatic and bactericidal activity, with concentrations ranging from 6.3% to >50% v/v [15].

Research has aimed to evaluate the efficacy of mupirocin in combination with other antibiotics, such as polymyxin B, both individually and in combination, both in vitro and in vivo, in rabbits

infected with *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. marcescens* keratitis, as evidenced by Morita et al. [14]. The results demonstrated that the combination of these antibiotics was effective against all three genera both in laboratory settings and within living organisms.

The present study revealed that the antibacterial activity of 50% and higher concentrations of Mupirocin against *E. faecalis* was significantly greater than that of Sandalwood oil in terms of activity against *P. aeruginosa*. Similarly, the antimicrobial activity of 0.39% and higher concentrations of sandalwood oil against *P. aeruginosa* was significantly greater than that of mupirocin in terms of activity against *E. faecalis*.

This suggests that both antimicrobial agents have antibacterial effects on the tested microbes at high concentrations and can be a drawback, as high concentrations might not be suitable for a patient's oral health and can lead to systemic complications [31,32].

Conclusion

Mupirocin and sandalwood oil have antibacterial properties that work against *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at high concentrations. Therefore, future studies can incorporate the synergistic action of mupirocin and sandalwood oil to be effective against the oral microflora at lower, appropriate concentrations.

Acknowledgement

This study was funded by Seed Money, Manipal Academy of Higher Education Manipal. The present study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Manipal College of Dental Sciences, Mangalore (approval number: 21018).

References

- Patil V, Akal N, Biradar S, Ratnakar P, Rairam S, Batta O. Comparative evaluation of antimicrobial efficacy of mushroom, Aloe vera, and Curcuma longa with calcium hydroxide as an intracanal medicament against *Enterococcus faecalis*: An in vitro study. *J Conserv Dent.*, 25(4), 415-419 (2022). doi: 10.4103/jcd.jcd_208_22
- Socransky SS, Gibbons RJ, Dale AC, Bortnick L, Rosenthal E, Macdonald JB. The microbiota of the gingival crevice area of man. I. Total microscopic and viable counts and counts of specific organisms. *Arch Oral Biol.*, 8, 275-80 (1963). doi: 10.1016/0003-9969(63)90019-0
- Madhubala MM, Srinivasan N, Ahamed S. Comparative evaluation of propolis and triantibiotic mixture as an intracanal medicament against *Enterococcus faecalis*. *J Endod.*, 37, 1287-9 (2011).
- Powers CN, Osier JL, McFeeters RL, Brazell CB, Olsen EL, Moriarity DM, Satyal P, Setzer WN. Antifungal and Cytotoxic Activities of Sixty Commercially Available Essential Oils. *Molecules*, 23(7), 1549 (2018). doi: 10.3390/molecules23071549
- Zuzarte M, Gonçalves MJ, Cavaleiro C, Canhoto J, Vale-Silva L, Silva MJ, Pinto E, Salgueiro L. Chemical composition and antifungal activity of the essential oils of *Lavandula viridis* L'Her. *J Med Microbiol.*, 60(Pt 5), 612-618 (2011). doi: 10.1099/jmm.0.027748-0
- Swamy MK, Akhtar MS, Sinniah UR. Antimicrobial Properties of Plant Essential Oils against Human Pathogens and Their Mode of Action: An Updated Review. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.* 2016, 3012462 (2016). doi: 10.1155/2016/3012462
- Varadan P, Ganesh A, Konindala R, Nagendrababu V, Ashok R, Deivanayagam K. Comparison of the Antibacterial Efficacy of Alexidine and Chlorhexidine Against *Enterococcus Faecalis*: An in Vitro Study. *Cureus*, 9(10), e1805 (2017). doi: 10.7759/cureus.1805
- Kim HS, Woo Chang S, Baek SH, Han SH, Lee Y, Zhu Q, Kum KY. Antimicrobial effect of alexidine and chlorhexidine against *Enterococcus faecalis* infection. *Int J Oral Sci.*, 5, 26-31 (2013). doi: 10.1038/ijos.2013.11
- Cogulu D, Uzel A, Oncag O, Aksoy SC, Eronat C. Detection of *Enterococcus faecalis* in Necrotic Teeth Root Canals by Culture and Polymerase Chain Reaction Methods. *Eur J Dent.*, 1(4), 216-21 (2007).
- Ghufran Ismail IBRAHIM, Hussein Ali JAWAD. Antimicrobial activity of Er,Cr:YSGG and Ultrasonic on *E. faecalis* biofilm in the mesial root canal systems of lower molars. *Braz Dent Sci.*, 27(1), e3904:1-11 (2024). doi: 10.4322/bds.2024.e3904

11. Pranati Tatekalva, Haripriya Subbaiyan, Shanmugam Rajesh Kumar. Comparative evaluation of antimicrobial potential of herbal extracts on *Streptococcus mutans* and *Enterococcus faecalis* An in vitro study. *Braz Dent Sci.*, 24(1), 1-7 (2021). doi: 10.14295/bds.2021.v24i1.2147
12. Ishikawa J, Horii T. Effects of mupirocin at subinhibitory concentrations on biofilm formation in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Chemotherapy*, 51(6), 361-2 (2005). doi: 10.1159/000088962
13. Horii T, Morita M, Muramatsu H, Muranaka Y, Kanno T, Maekawa M. Effects of mupirocin at subinhibitory concentrations on flagella formation in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Proteus mirabilis*. *J Antimicrob Chemother.*, 51(5), 1175-9 (2003). doi: 10.1093/jac/dkg226
14. Morita Y, Tomida J, Kawamura Y. Responses of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* to antimicrobials. *Front Microbiol.*, 4, 422 (2014). doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2013.00422
15. Man A, Santacroce L, Jacob R, Mare A, Man L. Antimicrobial Activity of Six Essential Oils Against a Group of Human Pathogens: A Comparative Study. *Pathogens.*, 8(1), 15 (2019). doi: 10.3390/pathogens8010015. Erratum in: *Pathogens.* 2019, 8(3)
16. Slocombe B, Perry C. The antimicrobial activity of mupirocin—an update on resistance. *J Hosp Infect.*, 19 Suppl B:19-25 (1991). doi: 10.1016/0195-6701(91)90198-b
17. Sutherland R, Boon RJ, Griffin KE, Masters PJ, Slocombe B, White AR. Antibacterial activity of mupirocin (pseudomonic acid), a new antibiotic for topical use. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.*, 27(4), 495-8 (1985). doi: 10.1128/AAC.27.4.495
18. Ira Widjiastuti, Setyabudi, Grace Angelina Samuel, Khadijah Fauzi Basalamah. The effect of calcium hydroxide in combination with propolis extract on decreasing nerve growth factor and substance P expression in rat dental pulp neuron. *Braz Dent Sci.*, 27(1), e4023:1-9 (2024). doi: 10.4322/bds.2024.e4023
19. Matthijs S, Vander Wauven C, Cornu B, Ye L, Cornelis P, Thomas CM, Ongena M. Antimicrobial properties of *Pseudomonas* strains producing the antibiotic mupirocin. *Res Microbiol.*, 165(8), 695-704 (2014). doi: 10.1016/j.resmic.2014.09.009
20. Fritz E, Fekete A, Lintelmann J, Schmitt-Kopplin P, Meckenstock RU. Isolation of two *Pseudomonas* strains producing pseudomonic acid A. *Syst Appl Microbiol.*, 32(1), 56-64 (2009). doi: 10.1016/j.syapm.2008.11.001
21. Borzini L, Condò R, De Dominicis P, Casaglia A, Cerroni L. Root Canal Irrigation: Chemical Agents and Plant Extracts Against *Enterococcus faecalis*. *Open Dent J.*, 10, 692-703 (2016). doi: 10.2174/1874210601610010692
22. Moreau JM, Conerly LL, Hume EB, Dajcs JJ, Girgis DO, Cannon BM, Thibodeaux BA, Stroman DW, O'Callaghan RJ. Effectiveness of mupirocin and polymyxin B in experimental *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Serratia marcescens* keratitis. *Cornea*, 21(8), 807-11 (2002). doi: 10.1097/00003226-200211000-00016
23. Love RM. *Enterococcus faecalis*—a mechanism for its role in endodontic failure. *Int Endod J.*, 34(5), 399-405 (2001). doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2591.2001.00437.x
24. Kishen A, Sum CP, Mathew S, Lim CT. Influence of irrigation regimens on the adherence of *Enterococcus faecalis* to root canal dentin. *J Endod.*, 34(7), 850-4 (2008). doi: 10.1016/j.joen.2008.04.006
25. Teixeira da Silva JA, Kher MM, Soner D, Page T, Zhang X, Nataraj M, Ma G. Sandalwood: basic biology, tissue culture, and genetic transformation. *Planta*, 243(4), 847-87 (2016). doi: 10.1007/s00425-015-2452-8
26. Azizan N, Mohd Said S, Zainal Abidin Z, Jantan I. Composition and Antibacterial Activity of the Essential Oils of *Orthosiphon stamineus* Benth and *Ficus deltoidea* Jack against Pathogenic Oral Bacteria. *Molecules*, 22(12), 2135 (2017). doi: 10.3390/molecules22122135
27. Takarada K, Kimizuka R, Takahashi N, Honma K, Okuda K, Kato T. A comparison of the antibacterial efficacies of essential oils against oral pathogens. *Oral Microbiol Immunol.*, 19(1), 61-4 (2004). doi: 10.1046/j.0902-0055.2003.00111.x
28. Ellen Roberta Lima Bessa, Ana Bessa Muniz, Lucas de Paula Ramos, Luciane Dias de Oliveira. Antifungal effect of *Quillaja saponaria* plant extract on biofilms of five *Candida* species of dental interest. *Braz Dent Sci.*, 27(3), e4233:1-9 (2024). doi: 10.4322/bds.2024.e4233
29. Chai WL, Hamimah H, Cheng SC, Sallam AA, Abdullah M. Susceptibility of *Enterococcus faecalis* biofilm to antibiotics and calcium hydroxide. *J Oral Sci.*, 49(2):161-6 (2007). doi: 10.2334/josnstd.49.161
30. Hughes J, Mellows G. Inhibition of isoleucyl-transfer ribonucleic acid synthetase in *Escherichia coli* by pseudomonic acid. *Biochem J.*, 176(1), 305-18 (1978). doi: 10.1042/bj1760305
31. Stuart CH, Schwartz SA, Beeson TJ, Owatz CB. *Enterococcus faecalis*: its role in root canal treatment failure and current concepts in retreatment. *J Endod.*, 32(2), 93-8 (2006). doi: 10.1016/j.joen.2005.10.049
32. Ranta K, Haapasalo M, Ranta H. Mono-infection of root canal with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Endod Dent Traumatol.*, 4(6), 269-72 (1988). doi: 10.1111/j.1600-9657.1988.tb00646.x